

The Role of Psychological Principles in Enhancing AI-Driven Security for Sustainable Development in Rivers State Owned Universities

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ABSTRACT: *The study investigated the role of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities. Three specific objectives and three research questions guided the study. This study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 35 lecturers from the two Rivers State owned universities. The entire population was used as sample size for the study. The data collecting instrument for this study is a self-structured questionnaire titled "Roles of Psychological Principles in Enhancing AI-driven Security Questionnaire." The instrument was structured using 4-point rating scale and was face and content validated any yielded an index reliability coefficient of 0.80 through Cronbach Alpha method. Mean, standard deviation and mean set were used to analyze the research questions. It was concluded that the role of psychological principles in AI-driven security is fundamental to building resilient and sustainable security infrastructure in universities. By leveraging psychological insights, universities can enhance security effectiveness, reduce vulnerabilities, and create a safer, more inclusive learning environment. The study made the following recommendations: universities should integrate behavioural analysis models into AI security systems to enhance real-time threat detection and universities should implement AI-powered security infrastructure that optimizes energy consumption and reduces operational costs.*

KEYWORDS: *Role, Psychological Principles, AI-Driven Security, Sustainable Development.*

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INTRODUCTION

In the digital age, higher institutions are increasingly vulnerable to security threats ranging from cyberattacks to physical safety breaches. As educational institutions become more technologically integrated, the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in security has expanded significantly. AI-driven security systems, powered by machine learning and behavioural analytics, have become essential tools in safeguarding academic environments. However, the effectiveness of this AI systems is greatly enhanced when psychological principles are incorporated into their development and application [1].

[2] opined that psychology plays a crucial role in understanding human behaviour, cognitive biases, and decision-making patterns and factors that directly influence security threats and responses. By integrating psychological insights into AI-driven security, higher institutions can develop more adaptive, predictive, and responsive security systems that go beyond traditional rule-based approaches. For instance, AI systems that analyze human behavioural patterns can detect potential threats such as cyber fraud, unauthorized access, or even early warning signs of violent incidents. Similarly, [3] averred that AI-driven

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cybersecurity frameworks can leverage psychological principles to understand and counteract social engineering tactics, phishing attempts, and insider threats.

According to [4] and [5] the role of psychology in AI-driven security extends beyond threat detection to improving user compliance and trust in security measures. Many security breaches occur due to human error, often linked to cognitive overload, negligence, or resistance to security protocols. By applying psychological insights, AI-driven security systems in higher institutions can be designed to enhance user engagement, minimize risk-prone behaviours, and promote a security-conscious culture among students, faculty, and administrative staff [6].

From a sustainable development perspective, [7] and [8] opine that AI-driven security systems that incorporate psychological principles contribute to long-term institutional stability, reducing the financial and reputational damage caused by security breaches. In the view of [9] and [10] a secure academic environment fosters research, innovation, and knowledge exchange and key pillars of sustainable development. As institutions continue to evolve in the digital era, integrating psychology into AI security frameworks will be essential in creating resilient, adaptive, and ethically sound security systems that support sustainable academic growth [11]. By this background, the study aims to provide a clearer understanding of the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development.

Statement of the Problem

Higher education institutions are increasingly reliant on digital technologies for administrations, research, and learning. However, this growing digital integration has also exposed these institutions to a wide range of security threats, including cyberattacks, unauthorized access, data breaches, and physical security risks. Traditional security measures, which often rely on static rule-based approaches, have proven inadequate in addressing the dynamic and evolving nature of these threats. As a result, artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as a crucial tool for enhancing security systems within higher institutions.

Despite the potential of AI-driven security solutions, many existing systems lack a deep understanding of human behaviour, decision-making patterns, and cognitive vulnerabilities and factors that significantly influence security risks. Psychological principles, which offer insights into human cognition, behaviour, and emotion, are often underutilized in AI security frameworks. This gap results in security systems that may fail to accurately predict and respond to threats posed by human actions, such as social engineering attacks, insider threats, and non-compliance with security protocols. Additionally, many security breaches occur due to human error, negligence, or resistance to security policies, underscoring the need for AI-driven security solutions that are designed with a psychological understanding of human behaviour. Moreover, security systems that do not consider psychological factors may face challenges in user adoption and trust. Many students, faculty, and staff members may resist or bypass security measures if they perceive them as intrusive, complex, or burdensome. This non-compliance weakens security frameworks and increases vulnerabilities. Additionally, ethical concerns related to privacy, bias, and psychological impact must be addressed to ensure that AI-driven security solutions do not infringe on individual rights or create unintended consequences.

Purpose of the Study

This study is aimed at investigating the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Identify some of the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities.
2. determine the psychological principles that can be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response in Rivers State owned universities for sustainable development.
3. examine the ways AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles can contribute to sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions provided direction for this study:

1. What are some of the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities?
2. How can psychological principles be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities?
3. In what ways can AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles, contribute to the sustainable development of Rivers State owned universities for sustainable development?

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of all the thirty-five (35) lecturers of Department of Educational Psychology in the two Rivers State owned universities namely, Rivers State University (RSU) and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUoE). Source: Academic Planning Unit of the Universities (2025 Report). A sample of thirty-five (35) lecturers comprising of 20 lecturers from RSU and 15 lecturers from IAUoE representing 100% of the population was selected. This sample was drawn through census sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire entitled: "Roles of Psychological Principles in Enhancing AI-driven Security Questionnaire (RPPEA-DSQ)". The instrument which had 15 items was structured with 4-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (1 point). The instrument was well validated and reliability index of 0.80 was obtained through Cronbach Alpha method. Mean, standard deviation and mean set were used to analyze the research questions.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What are some of the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities?

TABLE 1. Mean Responses of RSU and IAUoE Lecturers on the Roles of Psychological Principles in Enhancing AI-driven Security for Sustainable Development

S/N	Items	RSU Lecturers		IAUoE Lecturers		Mean Set for RSU/IAUoE Lecturers	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	STD	\bar{X}_2	STD		
1	Behavioural analysis for threat detection	2.78	1.04	3.33	0.58	3.06	A
2	Enhancing user compliance with security protocols	3.64	0.63	2.71	1.01	3.18	A
3	Reducing human error in security practices	2.44	0.95	3.67	0.58	3.06	A
4	Emotional intelligence in threat assessment	2.75	1.03	2.57	0.94	2.66	A
5	Psychological nudging for cybersecurity awareness	3.36	0.84	2.47	1.02	2.92	A
	Grand Mean/SD	2.99	0.90	2.95	0.83	2.98	A

Table 1 shows that all the items had weighted mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. Items 1 to 5 were accepted as the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities. The aggregate mean score 2.98 for both RSU and IAUoE lecturers was greater than the criterion mean indicated that the respondents shared the same opinion on the roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development. Therefore, roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities include the following: behavioural analysis for threat detection, enhancing user compliance with security protocols, reducing human error in security practices, emotional intelligence in threat assessment and psychological nudging for cybersecurity awareness.

Research Question 2: How can psychological principles be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities?

TABLE 2. Mean Responses of RSU and IAUoE Lecturers on how Psychological Principles can be Integrated into AI-driven Security Systems to Enhance Threat Detection and Response for Sustainable Development

S/N	Items	RSU		IAUoE		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	STD	\bar{X}_2	STD		
6	Cognitive load reduction in security interfaces	2.67	1.03	2.74	0.96	2.71	A
7	Social engineering awareness and AI defence mechanisms	2.78	0.97	2.70	0.80	2.74	A
8	Emotion recognition for risk assessment	2.74	0.89	2.65	0.86	2.70	A
9	Personalized security training programmes	2.63	0.95	2.59	0.92	2.61	A
10	Nudging techniques to promote secure behaviours	2.69	1.02	2.77	0.96	2.73	A
	Grand Mean/SD	2.70	0.97	2.69	0.90	2.70	A

Table 2 shows that all the items had weighted mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. Items 6 to 10 were accepted as the psychological principles that can be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities. The aggregate mean score 2.70 for both RSU and IAUoE lecturers was greater than the criterion mean indicated that the respondents shared the same opinion on the psychological principles that can be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response for sustainable development. Therefore, psychological principles can be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities through the following: cognitive load reduction in security interfaces, social engineering awareness and AI defence mechanisms, emotion recognition for risk assessment, personalized security training programmes and nudging techniques to promote secure behaviours.

Research Question 3: In what ways can AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles, contribute to the sustainable development of Rivers State owned universities for sustainable development?

TABLE 3. Mean Responses of RSU and IAUoE Lecturers on the Ways AI-driven Security Solutions, Informed by Psychology Principles can Contribute to the Sustainable Development

S/N	Items	RSU		IAUoE		Mean Set	Decision
		\bar{X}_1	STD	\bar{X}_2	STD		
11	Enhancing campus safety and crisis management	2.66	1.04	3.65	0.78	3.16	A
12	Reducing cybersecurity risks and data breaches	2.72	1.05	2.48	0.82	2.60	A
13	Promoting ethical and inclusive security policies	2.65	1.01	2.51	0.87	2.58	A
14	Increasing user compliance with security protocols	2.53	1.00	2.55	0.88	2.54	A
15	Enhancing mental well-being and psychological safety	2.51	0.77	2.67	1.16	2.59	A
	Grand Mean/SD	2.61	0.97	2.77	0.90	2.69	A

Table 3 shows that all the items had weighted mean scores that were greater than the criterion mean of 2.50. Items 7 to 15 were accepted as the ways AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles, can contribute for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities. The aggregate mean score 2.69 for both RSU and IAUoE lecturers was greater than the criterion mean indicated that the respondents shared the same opinion on the ways AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles, can contribute for sustainable development. Therefore, the ways AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles, can contribute for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities include the following: enhancing campus safety and crisis management, reducing cybersecurity risks and data breaches, promoting ethical and inclusive security policies, increasing user compliance with security protocols, and enhancing mental well-being and psychological safety.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study shows that roles of psychological principles in enhancing AI-driven security for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities include the following: behavioural analysis for threat detection, enhancing user compliance with security protocols, reducing human error in security practices, emotional intelligence in threat assessment and psychological nudging for cybersecurity awareness This agrees with [2] that psychology plays a crucial role in understanding human behaviour, cognitive biases, and decision-making patterns and factors that directly influence security threats and responses.

The study shows that psychological principles can be integrated into AI-driven security systems to enhance threat detection and response for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities through the following: cognitive load reduction in security interfaces, social engineering awareness and AI defence mechanisms, emotion recognition for risk assessment, personalized security training programmes and nudging techniques to promote secure behaviours. This is in corroboration with [3] that AI-driven cybersecurity frameworks can leverage psychological principles to understand and counteract social engineering tactics, phishing attempts, and insider threats.

The study shows that the ways AI-driven security solutions, informed by psychology principles, can contribute for sustainable development in Rivers State owned universities include the following: enhancing campus safety and crisis management, reducing cybersecurity risks and data breaches, promoting ethical and inclusive security policies, increasing user compliance with security protocols, and enhancing mental well-being and psychological safety. The finding is in support of [7] and [8] that through sustainable development perspective AI-driven security systems that incorporate psychological principles contribute to long-term institutional stability, reducing the financial and reputational damage caused by security breaches through.

CONCLUSION

The role of psychological principles in AI-driven security is fundamental to building resilient and sustainable security infrastructure in universities. By leveraging psychological insights, universities can enhance security effectiveness, reduce vulnerabilities, and create a safer, more inclusive learning environment. Moving forward, institutions must embrace interdisciplinary approaches that merge psychology, artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity to address emerging threats while promoting ethical and sustainable development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It was recommended that:

1. Universities should integrate behavioural analysis models into AI security systems to enhance real-time threat detection.
2. Universities should implement AI-powered security infrastructure that optimizes energy consumption and reduces operational costs.

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